

Position Control of a Three Degree of Freedom Robot Manipulator

Gökmen Katipoğlu¹, Savaş Takan²

¹Dokuz Eylül University, Computer Engineering Department, İzmir, Turkey

²Izmir Institute of Technology, Computer Engineering Department, Izmir, Turkey

Robotics is the area of science which analyzes appliances which are able to perform the desired task, to do physical acts and are supposed to replace man. Meanwhile Robotics is the shared technological area with all basic engineering fields. In order to have an understanding of robots' structure and fields of application, it is essential to use data network of basic engineering (including: mechanical, electricals and electronics, computer and industrial engineering). Robotics is the common outgrowth progressed and developed by all these engineering fields. In analyzing different stages of designing and making a robot one can see that it is the shared result of all engineering fields mentioned above.

Generally speaking, robot is a mechatronic device able to perform pre-determined tasks, in this study gradual development and general design of a hand robot is investigated.

This hand robot can be used for different intents. For instance it can perform as a classification robot. its mechanic structure allows this performance. Five different servo-assisted motors facilitate its movements in any particular way. Since biggest advantage of servo-assisted motors are the ability to make movements in the set angle by controller and high sensitivity. In this study, the movements of limbs in desired angles to desired points are computed using reverse kinematic equations. Atmega 2560 version of Arduino processors is applied as micro-processor. the main advantage of Atmega 2560 is allowing the robot hand to be used for different intents. also existence of different communication protocols which enables writing of different programs is another advantage. process speed of card makes it possible for the robot to perform better and lets the limbs to do desired action at the desired moment. for example if we decide to use it as a classification robot, it will be able to take out the material on the conveyor at the right moment and put them in the pre-determined spot. In the Home position it waits for newly arriving material by going backward. servo-assisted motors are used to make delicate actions like this possible. these motors are corresponded properly by Atmega 2560 to allow proper performance for robot.

Keywords: Forward kinematic, servo motor, arduino, microcontroller

1. INTRODUCTION

Robotics is the shared application area of engineering fields such as aerospace engineering, aircraft engineering, control engineering but it is mostly affected by mechanical electronic and mechatronic engineering fields. Robotics is the field of science which is dealing with developing the technology of electromechanical devices called robots and making it possible to use them in the desired area.

In its history, Ctesibius is accepted as the father of Robotics who has done pioneering projects in century. Ctesibius is the inventor of water clock which is more famous than him. He improved the existing water clock, his water clock was made up of a storage which was filling with water as a special rhythm. As the storage was filled the float inside ascended and the needle on tip of it marked this ascension on a cylinder.

Robotics began mechanical-based and continued with invention of electricity and then with the invention of electrical devices it conjoined electronics. Along with the technological developments, developments happened in robots' function and they started having more part in our daily lives because robots performed the action which they are programmed for directly, the error has been reduced drastically, so they are used to do every day chores or any kind of mass production projects. Even though the first that comes to mind as we hear robot is a device shaped and moving like human, resembling the most famous

'humanoid' robot Honda Asimo, but the features and functions of robot differs.

Robot is a mechanical device with electronic components performing as programmed under human control, nowadays they are mainly used in industrial production. In automotive industry many robots with distinct functioning are exploited. Generally used robots are manipulator type functioning ones. These organ shaped robots are used for functions like welding, assembly and painting.

Issac Asimov's robot series defined robots' creation as a mean of serving human beings. A robot's personal aims can never be preferred to those of human. This is stated as three robotics law. This law is the baseline for the ethical and legal relations among human and robots.

Law of Robotics:

1. a robot may not injure a human being or through inaction allow a human being to come to harm.
2. a robot must obey the orders, given to it by human beings except where such orders would conflict with the first law.
3. a robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the first or second law.

Robots are electronic devices able to detect their surroundings by their sensors, decide based on these detections perform as the made decision, and move or stop moving their organs as action. According to this definition a car controlled by a key board and linked with parallel

port to a computer is not a robot. Since it can not decide on its behalf and needs another one to control it. But if the car was able to use computer micro-processors to interpret the data received by sensors, and could make decision because it was able to perform independently would be a robot.

The first attempt to make industrial robot was made in the U.S. after 1950s along with Denavith and Hartenberg's kinematic calculating methods. In 1960s as a result of Stanford robot institute research different shapes of robots were developed and exploited in industry. Along with American firms like Cincinnati Mikron, Westinghouse, Unimation, Japanese firms such as Hitachi, Mitsubishi, Fanuc made their own robots and used them in production line. These resulted in creation of unimanipulator types like Puma, Scara, Yasuka- Motoman. Floor- fixed with certain moving space manipulators which worked with open kinematic chain, were robots able to do operations while moving popular as 'Mobile Robots'".

2. MODELLING OF THE MANIPULATOR

In this study the design of a cartesian type manipulator robot with three free angles on prototype manufacturing with kinematic equations calculation and its supporting software is investigated.

Figure 1. Modelling of the manipulator

Dimensions and kinematics of robot were controlled by developed kinematic method, to do so limb angles were given to check whether the parts reach the calculated point or not. Then using these angles as reference values, robot was run. It was noticed that the extreme points are reached theoretically calculated

extreme points and the reference angle is used to run the robot to check whether it reaches the extreme points or it's nearby and the result was affirmative. Robot's movements were made by Arduino microprocessor.

3. MICROCONTROLLERS

Microprocessor is a computer system which is combined on a single full circuit. A microprocessor includes CPU (mother board) RAM (random access memory) ROM (read only memory) timer, ADC (analogue digital converter), peripheral units like PWN, IO (input output units). Simple usage and not having a complex essential electric circuit is the main reason of its popularity since it almost has everything needed. Microprocessor is used to simplify complicated actions or automatic controlling. For instance the most basic electronic clocks, automatic washing machines, robots, cameras, LCD monitors, biomedical devices, industrial automation, electronic ticketing systems and the like electronic applications microprocessors are used.

Figure 2 Structure of microcontroller and its components

- Three basic actions performed by a microprocessor:
1. receiving various signals from the environment
 2. applying the received signals to pre-determined functions
 3. using the results of functions in the form of an action in outside world

Arduino data processing is a platform in which all the actions of transmission among various functional units or sending data to interfaces and open-sourced integrated circuit systems and basically programming related to a microprocessor is done.

Figure 3 Arduino Atmel micro-processor cards

4. THE PROCESS OF THE APPLICATION

At the start up of program the servo database is identified which includes information about each servo's specific timer unit, the number of functioning servos and signals of servos. When identification is done, servos are named. According to servos' angles the command are defined. In material identification an analogue system which calculates the distance of material on conveyor to check whether it has reached the distance defined as reachable for robot.

Loop waits for start command or 's' by the computer. Unless it is not given, sensors will be shut and servos will wait stable. As the letter s was given we entered the if loop and calculated servo motors' turning angles by using pre-established inverse kinematical locations. Then the in-line commands were written in the program to allow for robot to function fast. In if else loop servo-driver function was called for which with the given servo angles, sets servo motor's speed. It uses an internal loop to call for database and sends needed signals until gradually the desired angle is realized. Then starting over, waits for new material to reach the desired point. If the letter 'D' is pressed system take the initial position and waits.

Figure 4. Robot Manipulator recognizes the object

Figure 5. Robot Manipulator grasps the object

Figure 6. Robot Manipulator moves the object.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This article is prepared from the mechatronics master thesis called "POSITION CONTROL OF A THREE DEGREE OF FREEDOM ROBOT MANIPULATOR" by Gökmen KATIPOĞLU which is submitted to the Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences of Dokuz Eylül University. I would like to express my sincere appreciation to my supervisor Prof. Dr. Erol UYAR for his support and guidance from the beginning to the very end of this study. Under his guidance I had the chance to learn and improve myself in various subjects which I believe will be of great importance in my future academic studies and career.

REFERENCES

- [1] Çamoğlu, D. (2011). Bilgisayar kontrollü Robotik, Ankara: Dikey Eksen
- [2] Bingül, Z. ve Küçük, S. (2009). Robot kinematiği, İstanbul: Birsen Yayınevi
- [3] Kurtoğlu, A. (2011). Robot tekniği, Basım yeri: Papatya Yayınları
- [4] Wikipedia (b.t). Robotik, 20 Haziran 2013, <http://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robotik>
- [5] Wikipedia (b.t). Elektrik motoru, 20 Haziran 2013, <http://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robotik>
- [6] Wikipedia (b.t). Servo motor, 20 Haziran 2013, http://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Servo_motor